

A Managerial Insight into Selected Short Stories in Bengali Literature: A Case Analysis of “Subachani” by Bhagiratha Mishra

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ABSTRACT

The short story Subachani by Bhagiratha mishra is about an old lady in her 60s composing and singing scurrilous poems to raise emotional sentiments of wrong doers, residing in villages off the outskirts of Birbhum district in West Bengal. She was hired by people and politicians to bring ill fame to people committing wrong, or even as a broker to buy and sell goods or animals as a common trade practice.

The present research work is highlighted as a Case Analysis of the various tasks being rendered by an old tribal lady, whose attributes as a Rural Manager is highlighted in this work.

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INTRODUCTION

The author of the selected short story, Bhagiratha Mishra is a retired Government service holder, who had his postings in Rural Bengal. He observed people of versatile ethnicity residing in the rural areas of West Bengal.

Just of the story- A lady in her mid 60s is the central character of the story. She composes scurrilous poems, often acting as collaborative agent in order to settle problems cropping on and off the geographical periphery of the villages she reside. She is extremely poor financially, and is exploited vehemently by people in power and position, on and off the geographical boundary of her village.

She is a strong lady and endures with social politics and poverty that engulfs her. She acts as an outsourced individual who takes measures in-

Planning her communication style and modes of impeachment to reach rural people.

Organizing the efforts in synthesizing social harmony among Ethnic groups in the Society.

Staffing people from diverse backgrounds in the process of establishment of Group cohesiveness among individuals.

Directing her peers to raise the emotional sentiment levels of people belonging to her own ethnic community.

Coordinating her attributes in establishment of harmony, peace and cohesiveness among individuals of the same of different ethnic communities.

Reporting and Social budgeting of the efforts that she has synchronized in terms of inducing the moral perspective of the communal problems and roles as specified by people who pay her and use her as per requirements.

The lady , after reaching the age of 60, develops the disease of Clergyman’s sore throat, a disease which is recognized as occupational, Gomez Mejia, 1997 and eventually cancer which kills her, for which she gets help from no recognized sources.

Research Insights

Specific ethnic groups of the Bengali Society has composed poems, often on slang notes, to demean the ill –intentions of an individual or group of people.

After a prolonged study of the efforts as recognized by Subachani, the readers of the story are in a position to note that her Talent Management has never been taken seriously, and taking the stories of the author , (Mishra,B) as the benchmark, we could see that her employers thus vandalizing her skills of composing prose and poems, have channelized the same in wrong directions, thus exploiting her aesthetic sense of recognizing people skills.

As per the theory of Human Capital, (Schultz, T.A. 2002) Subachani suffers a huge setback and her efforts in recognizing her own creative Endeavour goes wasted.

Subachani as an employee is always sincere to her own efforts and performance in perspective of composition of songs, though scurrilous, and an agent in finalizing important deals.

The bauri ethnic tribal group has always composed prose and poems, the community to which Subachani belongs. This is an important insight towards loss of Human Capital (Schultz and others, 2007).

The language as spoken by Subachani is a colloquial Bengali, and extensive literature comprising of the same have been done by Dr. Kumar Rana , with the supportive aspects rendered by the Pratchi Educational Trust in Birbhum, a

body funded by Amartya Sen, et.al, the famous Nobel laureate in their works.

The cultural development of this kind has been mentioned by Jean Derez and Sen Amartya, in their paper entitled "Development as Freedom" (Derez J and Sen, A, 2000). Such languages and their regular enrichment has been encouraged by the team of experts from the Indian Institute of Rural Management, Anand, Gujarat.

The Ethnic tribal groups highlighted in the research inducing story, and their magnitude of poverty has been set as the backdrop image in the story. After utilizing and subsequently exploiting their services, the people like Subachani are thwarted towards the avenues of life with but little financial awards and gains. They are induced to beggary, and are fed with stale and rancid food, capitalizing upon the ill-sayings, as a societal bouncer, the role which Subachani plays in terms of the scanty pay that she receives.

